
Traceability for computationally-intensive metrology

Test for communication interfaces used for the exchange of metrological data

TraCIM Test

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Comprising the results from our research and the fruitful and intensive discussions with all our SmartCom project partners and stakeholders worldwide.

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1 Introduction

The PTB TraCIM (Traceability for Computationally-Intensive Metrology) online system [1] provides the test of data used for communication interfaces based on the D-SI (Digital SI) exchange format for the exchange of metrological data. The test is performed by checking against the requirements of D-SI [2].

For the test, a customer will request a test of data from the TraCIM system and a unique process key will be obtained. The customer transmits the data to be tested in the XML format and sends the data to the TraCIM system together with the process key. The TraCIM system automatically evaluates the units provided by the customer and checks the completeness of all the metrological information. After the TraCIM system assigns quality classes (medals) to the data, the system sends the report with the test results. The evaluation the test data is subject to section 2.

The data is exchanged with the TraCIM system by client-server communication (see section 3). The XML data schemata used for data exchange are described in section 4.

Placing an order requires access to a web shop (smartcom-tracim.ptb.de/tracim-server-2.0) for buying single test. After successful purchase of a test, a customer will get an order key that allows him to request a process key from the TraCIM system.

In order to check the functionality of the customer's TraCIM client, a charge free test suite with public testing including test results is provided. A registered customer is allowed to request the public test from the TraCIM system at any time in order to evaluate the correct function of his client-server communication. See section 3.2 on how to request public testing.

1.1 TraCIM system

The TraCIM online system [3] was established within the frame of an EURAMET project NEW06 TraCIM [4], funded by the European Union and is under strict quality control of TraCIM e.V.

Association. This system provided a tool for the validation of computational software applications used in metrology, e.g. testing of Gaussian and Chebyshev minimization algorithms [5, 6].

The TraCIM server allows users to validate their software directly at the point of use (e.g. on the measuring instrument itself) and at any time [7]. The test data and results will be exchanged via internet. A web interface is provided including a web shop. A client-server platform for testing metrological software has been developed enabling easy integration into existing software. This provides the user with a simple, automated validation process.

The SmartCom online validation system (SmartCom Expert Extension) was developed within the European joint research project EMPIR 17IND02 SmartCom [8]. It establishes a service that can be integrated into the TraCIM online system to test and certify XML documents. A practice guide [9] gives an introduction about integrating SmartCom online validation system into TraCIM. Unlike the test available so far on the current TraCIM system, any well-formed XML document can be validated, and test data are not generated.

2 Test result evaluation

2.1 Test scope

The data is tested for the use of SI units and the completeness of metrological information.

The data from the customer is provided in an XML format. It encodes values of measurement according to the XML reference implementation for the D-SI version 1.3.1 [10]. The verification of the customer data tests the building blocks for measurement data within the D-SI. These are the XML elements for real, constant, complex, list and hybrid quantities of measurement.

User-proprietary structures and information out of the scope of D-SI are not tested. The correctness of metrological information (e.g. numerical values and correct aggregation of data) is also not tested.

2.2 Medal of machine-readable metrology data

Metrological data provided by the D-SI data model are categorized into different quality classes of machine-readability, i.e. platinum, gold, silver, bronze and improvable [2]. The TraCIM server assigns the quality classes (medals) of the customer's data by evaluating the units and checking the completeness of all the metrological information. The assigned quality class is documented in the test report. The following quality classes (medals) can be achieved:

- Quality class PLATINUM
(All units refer to SI-base units and the metrological information is complete.)
- - Quality class GOLD

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(SI-derived units and SI-prefixes are used. The metrological information is complete.)

- - Quality class SILVER
(Non-SI units that are allowed with the 9th edition of the SI Brochure are used. The metrological information is complete.)
- - Quality class BRONZE
(Non-SI units deprecated by the 9th edition of the SI Brochure are used. The metrological information is complete.)
- - Quality class IMPROVABLE
(No SI units and/or wrong data types are used. The metrological information is incomplete.)

The platinum quality class corresponds to the strongest eligibility for an unambiguous and safe exchange of metrological data in machine communication. This eligibility decreases more and more with the medal designations gold, silver, and bronze. The transfer of metrological data from the class “improvable” is erroneous and chaotic as the exchanged information is incomplete and ambiguous. A machine may not be able to interpret this metrological data without human interference. Attributes such as “Next Generation” or dates are also associated with the quality classes. These attributes symbolise to users that the conversion of established data structures can take place in appropriate periods. New users are recommended to strive for the platinum quality class. A quality class is only reached if all metrological data that are digitally transmitted meet the requirements of that class [2].

- **Platinum** – also known as “Next Generation” - is the purest form of digital exchange of metrological data. In addition to the specifications of the seven SI base units, seven important units, i.e. the unit “one”, the units “degree”, “minute” and “second” for angles, and the units “day” and “minute” for

quantities of time, are permitted in this quality class. This set of units is denoted as “SI++ units”. Prefixes, on the other hand, are not allowed in the Platinum class.

- **Gold** – also called “2030” – basically enables the exchange of values with the specification of SI++ units extended by using SI prefixes and SI derived units, according to the specifications of the SI brochure [11].
- **Silver** – also called “2024” – allows the exchange of values with the specification of SI++ units, SI prefixes, SI derived units and other units outside of the SI that are permitted to be used together with the SI.
- **Bronze** – also known as “2020” - enables the exchange of digital measurement data by specifying a measured value and an outdated unit from the previous edition of the SI brochure [12] in the SI unit format. The units that can be used for the bronze medal are non-SI units that have once been allowed to be used with the SI but were deprecated in the latest edition of the SI brochure [11].
- **Improvable** – allows the exchange of measurement data without adhering to the formats described above. This includes the indication of measured values without the indication of a unit, the indication of measured values in a number system outside the decimal system or the separation of decimal and decimal places by a comma or other non-permitted characters.

When the achieved quality class is not “PLATINUM”, a detailed list of individual evaluation results, which led to the overall test results, will be given in the appendix to the test report. Appendix A summaries all medals and notifications which may be given in the appendix of the test report.

2.3 Test of D-SI elements in the DCC

The TraCIM online system can also provide the test for the use of SI units in a DCC (Digital Calibration Certificate). The test is performed by checking the usage of all D-SI elements in the DCC XML against the requirement of D-SI [2].

Most of the test scope of the D-SI element in the DCC is the same as that in section 2.1. The customer should provide a DCC in the XML format as the data to be tested. The server will parse the DCC provided by the customer. Then, the server will evaluate all the units used in the DCC and check the completeness of all the metrology information. Finally, the server will assign medals of data and send report to the customer. The medal system is described in section 2.2.

The TraCIM online system does not validate the DCC with the underlying XML Scheme Definition (XSD) for the conformity of the unified DCC syntax [13].

3 Client-server communication

The test procedure is highly automated using internet-based data exchange by client-server communication. Through a client application, the user can get a process key and send back the data for testing. The TraCIM system server automatically handles requests. The necessary communication between client and server to perform a single test is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Message exchange.

The data exchanged between client and server is encapsulated within XML. A proper specification of the applied XML data schema is subject to section 4. During processing messages are treated as plain character strings send between the client application and the TraCIM system server.

3.1 Development of a client application

Configuration of the HTTPS connection:

For communication with the TraCIM server, the client application must use an HTTPS (Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure = encrypted HTTP) connection that allows to send and receive content in the form of character strings containing messages in XML format. Each HTTPS connection is created from a specific URL (Uniform Resource Locator) regarding requests for process key.

After opening the connection according to the URL, the following configurations must be done:

- Enable output and input operations for the connection
- Set the request method “POST” (request comprising input and output)
- Set connection property “content-Type” to “application/xml”
- Set connection property “accept” to “application/xml”
- Set connection property “content-length” to the amount of characters of the content that is send to the TraCIM system.

Packages for creation and configuration of an HTTPS connection are available for different programming languages such as for (examples):

- Java: java.net API (URLConnection)
- C/C++: Microsoft C++ REST SDK (“Casablanca”) or similar
- C#: System.Net (.NET 4.5: System.Net.Http) Assembly

POST request for obtaining process key:

The URL of an HTTPS connection for POST request in order to obtain a process key for activating one test is

https://smartcom-tracim.ptb.de/tracim-server-2.0/api/order/<SMARTCOM_ORDER_KEY>/test

where <SMARTCOM_ORDER_KEY> has to be replaced by a valid SmartCom D-SI test order key. After creation and configuration of a connection as described above the client application has to send the request message. When the TraCIM system receives the client message it will start creating a unique process key. The process key is returned to the client.

In the case a customer is not properly registered at the TraCIM system or incorrect order keys were submitted the TraCIM server will send an error message.

Client content and TraCIM system content for retrieving the process key are presented in sections 4.2 and 4.3. Error messages are presented in section 4.6.

POST request for sending test data and obtaining the certificate:

The URL of an HTTPS connection for a POST request in order to send data for testing and obtain the certificate for testing result is

https://smartcom-tracim.ptb.de/tracim-server-2.0/api/test/<PROCESS_KEY>

where <PROCESS_KEY> must be replaced by the individual process key that was returned by the TraCIM system.

The client will prepare the XML content (process key, type of data, data to be tested) to be attached to the POST request and will send it to the TraCIM system.

The TraCIM system will receive and evaluate the content and generate a result message that states whether the test is passed, or otherwise contains an error outline.

In case of a passed test, the data send to the client contains the test report as a PDF document encoded in XML. This test report gives detailed information on the quality class (medal) that was achieved by the tested data.

In case of a sample test request, the PDF test report is not signed and does not contain the PTB seal.

For the case of an improper process key, the TraCIM system returns an error message (see section 4.6). In this case, the customer can fix the problems and send the test data again. For the case of a malformed or incomplete XML content, the test result is not passed, and the SmartCom Expert Extension returns an error message for the PDF test report (see section 4.5). In such cases, the associated process key is invalid.

Client content and TraCIM system content for sending the client data for testing and PDF report are presented in sections 4.4 and 4.5. Error messages are presented in section 4.6.

! TraCIM service for testing is limited in time. After receiving an order key, a customer has a total of 200 days for performing the test. After 20, 120 and 180 days the TraCIM system will automatically send warning messages to the customer e-mail address stating the remaining time for testing. When the access period of a test expired, a final information is sent to the customer.

3.2 Public testing

Public testing denotes a SmartCom test for backtracking errors within the client application that could compromise a commercial test. For any registered customer the public test is free of charge with unlimited request amount. In comparison to a test with commercial test data the certificate returned by the server is not countersigned by PTB as legally valid certificate.

The sample order key is available for registered customers. Please check the website (<https://smartcom-tracim.ptb.de/tracim-server-2.0>) or send an email to smartcom-tracim@ptb.de for further information.

4 XML message content

4.1 TraCIM schemata

The XML schemata which specify the format of the XML files for the exchange of metrological data with the TraCIM system can be obtained from the following URL's:

<https://tracim.ptb.de/tracim/api/schema/tracim.xsd> ¹⁾

Notes:

¹⁾ Report schema

It is strongly recommended, that a customer uses these schemas in order to test client functions during client development.

4.2 Test request

The XML schema below shows the complete message for the initial test request by the client application. The message is an empty TraCIM message.

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8" standalone="yes"?>
<tracim:tracim
  xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance"
  xmlns:tracim="http://tracim.ptb.de/tracim">
</tracim:tracim>
```

4.3 Transmission process key

The process key returned by the TraCIM system is composed according to an XML schema with two major elements for order identification and process identification. The order elements

contain the order key, the date of the creation of the test and a date for the expiration of the test (deadline for sending test results for evaluation). The process element contains the process key associated with the test request. The test element contains an element that is not used by the SmartCom test.

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8" standalone="yes"?>
<tracim:tracim
  xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance"
  xmlns:smartcom-test=
    "http://smartcom.ostfalia.de/smartcom/test"
  xmlns:tracim="http://tracim.ptb.de/tracim">

  <tracim:order>
    <tracim:key>[ORDER_KEY]</tracim:key>
    <tracim:creationDate>[...]</tracim:creationDate>
    <tracim:expirationDate>[...]</tracim:expirationDate>
  </tracim:order>

  <tracim:process>
    <tracim:key>[PROCESS_KEY]</tracim:key>
  </tracim:process>

  <tracim:test>
    <smartcom-test:payload>SmartCom    doesn't    need    test
data</smartcom-test:payload>
  </tracim:test>

</tracim:tracim>
```

4.4 Client data for validation

The client data for validation must be sent to the TraCIM system as XML string compliant with the XML schema for the SmartCom result. The client must specify the following information:

- **[PROCESS_KEY]:** process key received in message from section 4.3.
- **[TYPE]:** The type of data that is send for testing. This could be an identifier for the data format used by the client.

The data to be tested is provided within the XML element `<smartcom-result:payload>`. The data must be structured in a valid XML format. It must use the XML namespace `xmlns:si=https://ptb.de/si` for all components referring to the D-SI metadata format and the namespace must be given either as an attribute of the payload element or within the customer data.

Below is an example of the D-SI test XML string which has to be sent to the TraCIM server.

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8" standalone="yes"?>
<smartcom-result:smartComResult
  xmlns:smartcom-result=
    "http://smartcom.ostfalia.de/smartcom/result"
  xmlns:tracim="http://tracim.ptb.de/tracim"
  xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance">

  <smartcom-result:processKey>[PROCESS_KEY]
    </smartcom-result:processKey>

  <smartcom-result:type>[TYPE]</smartcom-result:type>

  <smartcom-result:payload xmlns:si="https://ptb.de/si">

    <si:complex>
      <si:label>a label</si:label>
      <si:valueMagnitude>2</si:valueMagnitude>
      <si:valuePhase>1</si:valuePhase>
      <si:unit>\metre</si:unit>
      <si:unitPhase>\degree</si:unitPhase>
      <si:dateTime>2018-09-27T13:00:00</si:dateTime>
    </si:complex>
```

```
</smartcom-result:payload>
```

```
</smartcom-result:smartComResult>
```

When the D-SI metadata format is in a DCC, the XML namespace `xmlns:dcc=https://ptb.de/dcc` must be provided in the XML element `<smartcom-result:payload>`. The other structures of XML elements `<smartcom-result:processKey>` and `<smartcom-result:type>` are the same. Below is an example for DCC validation, where the data are extracted from the XML element `<smartcom-result:payload>`.

```
<smartcom-result:payload xmlns:si="https://ptb.de/si">
```

```
<dcc:digitalCalibrationCertificate
  xmlns:dcc="https://ptb.de/dcc"
  xsi:schemaLocation="https://ptb.de/dcc
    https://ptb.de/dcc/v2.3.0/dcc.xsd"
  schemaVersion="2.3.0">

  <dcc:administrativeData>[...]</dcc:administrativeData>
  <dcc:measurementResults>
    [...]
    <dcc:quantity>
      [...]
      <si:complex>
        <si:label>a label</si:label>
        <si:valueMagnitude>2</si:valueMagnitude>
        <si:valuePhase>1</si:valuePhase>
        <si:unit>\metre</si:unit>
        <si:unitPhase>\degree</si:unitPhase>
        <si:dateTime>2018-09-27T13:00:00</si:dateTime>
      </si:complex>
      [...]
    </dcc:quantity>
    [...]
  </dcc:measurementResults>
```

```
</dcc:digitalCalibrationCertificate>
```

```
</smartcom-result:payload>
```

If an invalid XML format is provided within the XML element `<smartcom-result:payload>`, then the test evaluation result will be not passed. The process key cannot be re-used of the test.

If the user is not providing information on the type of the data and leaves the field `<smartcom-result:type>` empty, then the SmartCom D-SI test will interpret the type of data by default as a “data fragment”. The test report will then display “N/A” for the type of tested data.

4.5 Test report

After evaluation the TraCIM system returns XML data according to an XML schema with the test results. It comprises the three elements:

- **passed**
true, if the client data passed the test successfully, else false
- **report**
character string with the medal that was achieved by the tested data ('PLATINUM', 'GOLD', 'SILVER', 'BRONZE' or 'IMPROVABLE'. If malformed XML was provided for test data, then this element has the value 'Malformed / illegal XML' or an information If the tested data was malformed XMLshort report on the test evaluation
- **reportPDF**
character string with the test report PDF

In order to create the test report PDF document as PDF file, the “reportPDF” character string ('base64' encoded – check

programming language objects/methods) can be converted and written to a new file with the proper “.pdf” file name extension.

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8" standalone="yes"?>
<tracim:tracim
  xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance"
  xmlns:tracim="http://tracim.ptb.de/tracim">

  <tracim:validation>

    <tracim:passed>true</tracim:passed>
    <tracim:report>[...]</tracim:report>
    <tracim:reportPDF>1)JKD5iuD98IHh[...]</tracim:reportPDF>

  </tracim:validation>

</tracim:tracim>
```

Note: ¹⁾ 'base64' encoded

4.6 TraCIM error messages

The following XML code is sent by the server in case of errors, where [error code] and [error description] are replaced with values according to table in Appendix B (after the XML excerpt). Table B.1 lists the corresponding error code and error description.

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8" standalone="yes"?>
<tracim:tracim
  xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance"
  xmlns:tracim="http://tracim.ptb.de/tracim">

  <tracim:error>
    <tracim:code>[error code]</tracim:code>
    <tracim:description>[error description]
      </tracim:description>
  </tracim:error>
```

</tracim:tracim>

In case an error message is received, the error description may contain useful hints what caused the error.

5 Test report

The certificate can be extracted from the string stream ('base64' encoded; see section 4.5, XML tag 'tracim: reportPDF') into a PDF file ready for printing. The layout follows the rules for test reports as used in the PTB (official header, legal statements etc.).

The test report PDF is only issued if the test is passed.

6 How to get support

Support is provided by e-mail at

smartcom-tracim@ptb.de

The support comprises

- provider support (contact, fees, etc.)
- technical support for client software
- support regarding the **D-SI** data model

7 Legal and copyright information

Copyright for this document: PTB. The document content is subject to change without notice.

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Appendix A Medal and error messages

Table A.1 Medal and error messages with IDs cf and ci

Scope	Type	Error ID	Medal	Error message	Description (Broken D-SI rule IDs) ¹⁾
Coverage Factor	Error	cf-1 ²⁾	Improvable	Coverage factor must be greater than one or equal to one	R005
Coverage Interval	Error	ci-1 ²⁾	Improvable	Standard uncertainty must have a positive value	Also used with si:constant uncertainty, R004
Coverage Interval	Error	ci-2	Improvable	Invalid bounds of coverage interval	R027

Table A.2 Medal and error messages with IDs cm and cn

Scope	Type	Error ID	Medal	Error message	Description (Broken D-SI rule IDs) ¹⁾
Covariance Matrix	Error	cm-1	Improvable	Covariance value <value> has invalid correlation value > 1	R034
Covariance Matrix	Error	cm-2	Improvable	Negative element values in main diagonal of covariance matrix not permitted.	R004
Covariance Matrix	Error	cm-3	Improvable	Invalid dimension of covariance matrix found in si:complex	R033
Covariance Matrix	Error	cm-4	Improvable	Invalid dimension of covariance matrix found in si:list	R033

Continued on the next page

Table A.2 Medal and error messages with IDs cm and cn - continued

Scope	Type	Error ID	Medal	Error message	Description (Broken D-SI rule IDs) ¹⁾
Covariance Matrix	Error	cm-5	Improvable	Non-quadratic covariance matrix found.	R033
Covariance Matrix	Error	cm-6	Improvable	Non-symmetric covariance matrix found.	R033
Covariance Matrix	Error	cm-7	Improvable	Unit <unit> in covariance matrix is not valid for underlying vector quantity.	R035
Constant	Error	cn-1	Improvable	Use of distribution without uncertainty component	R025

Table A.3 Medal and error messages with IDs co and cp

Scope	Type	Error ID	Medal	Error message	Description (Broken D-SI rule IDs) ¹⁾
Complex	Error	co-1 ²⁾	Improvable	Mixed usage of Cartesian and polar complex form	R001, R024
Complex	Error	co-2 ²⁾	Improvable	Incomplete Cartesian complex form	R024
Complex	Error	co-3 ²⁾	Improvable	Incomplete polar complex form	R024
List of Complex	Error	co-4	Improvable	Insufficient dimension of vector quantity with bivariate uncertainty found in si:list	R037
List of Complex	Error	co-5	Improvable	Global Bivariate Uncertainty and Region defined in si:list	R036

Continued on the next page

Table A.3 Medal and error messages with IDs co and cp- continued

Scope	Type	Error ID	Medal	Error message	Description (Broken D-SI rule IDs) ¹⁾
List of Complex	Error	co-6	Improvable	Insufficient dimension of vector quantity with multivariate uncertainty found in si:list	R040
List of Complex	Error	co-7	Improvable	Illegal mixture of local uncertainty statements and list uncertainty statements found in si:list	R051
List of Complex	Error	co-8 ²⁾	Improvable	si:list is empty but should contain at least one complex element	R001, R043
List of Complex	Error	co-9 ²⁾	Improvable	Illegal use of univariate uncertainty in list of complex	R030

Continued on the next page

Table A.3 Medal and error messages with IDs co and cp - continued

Scope	Type	Error ID	Medal	Error message	Description (Broken D-SI rule IDs) ¹⁾
List of Complex	Error	co-10	Improvable	Mandatory list units missing for bivariate uncertainty in si:list	R039
List of Complex	Error	co-11	Improvable	Complex elements in si:list must be of Cartesian coordinate form	R041, R046
List of Complex	Error	co-12	Improvable	Complex elements in si:list must be of polar coordinate form	R041, R046
List of Complex	Error	co-13	Improvable	Insufficient number of complex elements in si:list with list units	R044, R045
List of Complex	Error	co-14	Improvable	Use of listUnitPhase without listUnit not permitted	R047

Continued on the next page

Table A.3 Medal and error messages with IDs co and cp - continued

Scope	Type	Error ID	Medal	Error message	Description (Broken D-SI rule IDs) ¹⁾
Coverage Probability	Error	cp-1 ²⁾	Improvable	Coverage Probability must be within the interval [0, 1]	R006

Table A.4 Medal and error messages with IDs eu

Scope	Type	Error ID	Medal	Error message	Description (Broken D-SI rule IDs) ¹⁾
Expanded Uncertainty	Error	eu-1 ²⁾	Improvable	Expanded uncertainty must have a positive value	R004

Table A.5 Medal and error messages with IDs hy

Scope	Type	Error ID	Medal	Error message	Description (Broken D-SI rule IDs) ¹⁾
Hybrid	Error	hy-1 ²⁾	Improvable	Hybrid must have at least one element	R052

Table A.6 Medal and error messages with IDs li

Scope	Type	Error ID	Medal	Error message	Description (Broken D-SI rule IDs) ¹⁾
List of List	Error	li-1 ²⁾	Improvable	si:list of si:lists should not have a list unit or list unit phase	R002, R044, R045
List of List	Error	li-2 ²⁾	Improvable	si:list of si:lists should not have a univariate (respectively bivariate) list uncertainty	R002, R030, R038
List of List	Error	li-3	Improvable	Illegal mixture of local phase units and list phase units found in si:list	R049
List of List	Error	li-4	Improvable	Illegal mixture of local units and list units found in si:list	R048, R049

Continued on the next page

Table A.6 Medal and error messages with IDs li- continued

Scope	Type	Error ID	Medal	Error message	Description (Broken D-SI rule IDs) ¹⁾
List of List	Error	li-5	Improvable	Phase units are missing in si:list	R049
List of List	Error	li-6	Improvable	Units are missing in si:list	R049
List of List	Error	li-7 ²⁾	Improvable	Not permitted elements found in list	R042, R043
List of List	Error	li-8 ²⁾	Improvable	si:list of si:lists should not provide a multivariate uncertainty	R040

Table A.7 Medal and error messages with IDs re

Scope	Type	Error ID	Medal	Error message	Description (Broken D-SI rule IDs) ¹⁾
Real	Error	re-1 ²⁾	Improvable	Missing mandatory elements in real format	R001
List of Real	Error	re-2	Improvable	Illegal mixture of local uncertainty statements and list uncertainty statements found in si:list	R050
List of Real	Error	re-3 ²⁾	Improvable	si:list is empty	R001, R043
List of Real	Error	re-4	Improvable	Insufficient dimension of vector quantity with multivariate uncertainty found in si:list	R040

Continued on the next page

Table A.7 Medal and error messages with IDs re- continued

Scope	Type	Error ID	Medal	Error message	Description (Broken D-SI rule IDs) ¹⁾
List of Real	Error	re-5	Improvable	List univariate uncertainty and region defined in si:list	R028
List of Real	Error	re-6	Improvable	Univariate uncertainty with less than two real elements in si:list	R029
List of Real	Error	re-7	Improvable	Mandatory list units missing for univariate uncertainty in si:list	R031
List of Real	Error	re-8 ²⁾	Improvable	Illegal use of bivariate uncertainty in si:list of si:real	R038
List of Real	Error	re-9	Improvable	Insufficient number of real elements in si:list with list units	R044

Table A.8 Medal and error messages with IDs st

Scope	Type	Error ID	Medal	Error message	Description (Broken D-SI rule IDs) ¹⁾
Distribution	Error	st-1	None	Distribution should contain a value when it is defined	R023

Table A.9 Medal and error messages with IDs up

Scope	Type	Error ID	Medal	Error message	Description (Broken D-SI rule IDs) ¹⁾
Unit Phase	Error	up-1	Improvable	No unit identified for phase angle.	R016
Unit Phase	Error	up-2	Improvable	Unit <unit> not permitted in Unit Phase.	R016
Unit Phase	Error	up-3	Improvable	Exponent \tothe{<exponent>} is not permitted with \metre in Unit Phase	R016
Unit Phase	Info	None	Gold	Unit class GOLD	R016, R054

Table A.10 Medal and error messages with IDs ut.

Scope	Type	Error ID	Medal	Error message	Description (Broken D-SI rule IDs) ¹⁾
Unit	Error	ut-1 ²⁾	Improvable	unit is empty	R007
Unit	Error	ut-2	None	illegal escape sequence \t \n \r	R007
Unit	Error	ut-3	Improvable	Usage of unknown identifier "<identifier>"	R007
Unit	Error	ut-4	Improvable	Using unit <unit> with prefix <prefix> is not permitted	R010, R011, R012
Unit	Error	ut-5	Improvable	Usage of prefix <prefix> without unit	R008, R009

Continued on the next page

Table A.10 Medal and error messages with IDs ut - continued

Scope	Type	Error ID	Medal	Error message	Description (Broken D-SI rule IDs) ¹⁾
Unit	Error	ut-6	Improvable	Using unit <unit> with exponent \tothe{<exponent>} is not permitted	R013, R014
Unit	Error	ut-7	Improvable	Usage of exponent \tothe{<exponent>} without unit	R008
Unit	Error	ut-8	Improvable	Unit has not permitted number of prefixes	R015
Unit	Info	None	Gold	Unit class GOLD	R018, R054
Unit	Info	None	Silver	Unit class SILVER	R019
Unit	Info	None	Bronze	Unit class BRONZE	R020

Table A.11 Medal and XML error messages

Scope	Type	Medal	XML error message	Description (Broken D-SI rule IDs) ¹⁾
Coverage Factor	Error	Improvable	XML well formed but violates schema (not a valid si element): org.xml.sax.SAXParseException: cvc-pattern-valid: Value <vale> is not facet-valid with respect to pattern '\+?([1-9]\d*\.\d*) ([1-9]\d*)' for type 'kValueType'.	R005
Coverage Probability	Error	Improvable	XML well formed but violates schema (not a valid si element): org.xml.sax.SAXParseException: cvc-pattern-valid: Value <value> is not facet-valid with respect to pattern '\+?((0(\.\d*)?) (1(\.0*)?))' for type 'probabilityValueType'.	R006

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Table A.11 Medal and XML error messages. - continued

Scope	Type	Medal	XML error message	Description (Broken D-SI rule IDs) ¹⁾
Standard uncertainty	Error	Improvable	XML well formed but violates schema (not a valid si element): org.xml.sax.SAXParseException: cvc-pattern-valid: Value <value> is not facet-valid with respect to pattern '\+?((\d*\.\d+) (\d+\.\d*)) (\d+\. ?) ([Ee][-+]?(\d+)?' for type 'uncertaintyValueType'	Also used with expanded uncertainty and si:constant uncertainty, R004
Uncorrected sequence of components	Error	Improvable	XML well formed but violates schema (not a valid si element): org.xml.sax.SAXParseException: cvc-complex-type.2.4.a: Invalid content was found starting with element '{"https://ptb.de/si":<element>}'. One of '{"https://ptb.de/si":<element>}' is expected.	R001, R002

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Table A.11 Medal and XML error messages. - continued

Scope	Type	Medal	XML error message	Description (Broken D-SI rule IDs) ¹⁾
Uncorrected sequence of components	Error	Improvable	XML well formed but violates schema (not a valid si element): org.xml.sax.SAXParseException: cvc-complex-type.2.4.b: The content of element <element> is not complete. One of '{\"https://ptb.de/si\":<element>}' is expected.	R001, R002

Note to table A.1 - table A.11

¹⁾ This column only gives the broken **D-SI** rule IDs. The specific description of these rules can be found in Appendix C [2].

²⁾ The XML error message in table A.11 from SmartCom Expert Extension may be attached in test report instead of error message with error ID.

Appendix B Error messages of TraCIM server

Table B.1 Error messages ¹⁾ of TraCIM system

[error code]	[error description]
403	No more tests left for this test process.
403	Test process already closed.
403	Test Data already used.
404	Unknown order number.
422 ²⁾	Unknown request type. Consult specific message.
422 ²⁾	Process key does not match!

Continued on next page

Table B.1 Error messages ¹⁾ of TraCIM system – continued

[error code]	[error description]
500	Internal Server error.

Note to table B.1

¹⁾ Column [error code]: these codes are identical with the HTTP error codes. As one code can describe more than one reason, multiple lines with the same code are present; details can be found in the next column ([error description]).

Column [error description]: a textual explanation of the error reason.

²⁾ For this code, a 'frame message' will be generated – 'Sorry, but your request could not be interpreted. Please check your message or contact the support. The system says: ' [error description]

Please note: if, due to specific reasons, the server cannot generate a proper XML error message, please check the HTML response of the server. This can be done, i.e. with programming the client for processing both XML and HTML messages.

Appendix C Rules for the use of the D-SI version 1.3 in short

This document summarises the rules for the application of the D-SI metadata model version 1.3. In addition, it includes an outline of implementation details of the XML reference scheme referring to version 1.3.1.

All rules for the use of the D-SI have a unique identifier (beginning with letter 'R') accompanied by a short description with all necessary technical details. The aspects for the XML reference implementation are written in italic.

The list of rules is supplemented by a list of data requirements that are in the responsibility of the user of the D-SI (identifiers beginning with letter 'D') and a list of all data models in the D-SI (identifiers beginning with letter 'M').

General rules

R001

All mandatory components of elements in the D-SI must be provided. In the atomic representation the minimum requirement is to provide a value and a unit. The mandatory elements are listed in data models M01 – M13.

XML: The required mandatory components are defined by the XML scheme and can be validated by the scheme. An exception for the validation is the combination of units in lists with real and complex elements (see rules R048 and R049).

R002

The components of the D-SI elements shall be provided in the sequence as defined in the D-SI data model diagrams starting with the first component on the left side and then going to the right. The proper sequence of elements is listed in data models M01 – M13.

XML: The correct sequence of components is defined by the XML scheme.

R003

Numerical values shall be of decimal format using digits '0-9', optional preliminary sign ('+' or '-'), dot as decimal separator and optional an exponent starting with the identifier 'e' or 'E' followed by an exponent value (digits '0-9' and optional sign '+' or '-'). The number of decimal digits is not limited, and no blank spaces shall be contained. This rule applies to the components 'value', 'intervalMin', 'intervalMax', 'valueReal', 'valueImag', 'valueMagnitude', 'valuePhase' and covariance values (non-main diagonal values in covariance matrix element).

XML: Decimal values are based on the format for double values provided by the XML specification. Expressions like NaN, INF and null are not permitted.

R004

Numerical values for uncertainties shall be positive (or zero) values in the general decimal format which is defined in Rule R003. The values shall be greater than or equal to zero. This rule applies to components 'uncertainty', 'standardUnc' and variance values (main diagonal values in covariance matrix element).

XML: The correct type is defined by a constraint of the double format from the XML specification.

R005

Numerical values for coverage factors shall be positive values greater than or equal to one based on the general decimal format which is defined in Rule R003. The value shall not be written with an exponent. This rule applies to all 'coverageFactor' components.

XML: The XML uses for all coverage factor components the double format from the XML specification which is constrained to values greater or equal to one through a regular expression.

R006

Numerical values for coverage probabilities shall be values greater than or equal to zero and less than or equal to one based on the

general decimal format which is defined in Rule R003. An exponent is not permitted. This rule applies to all 'coverageProbability' components.

XML: The correct type is defined by a constraint of the double format from the XML specification.

R007

All units shall be provided in SI units using the formal unit language (SI format) from the Digital System of Units (D-SI) booklet (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.3522631). They must be written as UTF-8 encoded string in lower case without blank spaces, tabs or carriage returns. This rule applies to the components 'unit', 'unitPhase', 'listUnit', 'listUnitPhase'. When using 'hybrid' elements, the rule only applies to units inside the first element in hybrid.

XML: The unit strings used in XML shall not corrupt the requirements for a valid XML structure. The XML shall use encoding UTF-8. Requires external validation.

R008

The basic structure of a unit in the SI format must consist of units listed in the BIPM SI brochure (8th and 9th edition). It is allowed to add a prefix prior to each BIPM SI unit and an exponent after each BIPM SI unit. Combined unit expression can be created from arithmetic multiplication of multiple BIPM SI units (including associated prefix and exponent). Details on the use of units are given by rules R009 to R020.

XML: The unit strings used in XML shall not corrupt the requirements for a valid XML structure. The XML shall use encoding UTF-8. Requires external validation.

R009

Each BIPM SI unit shall have not more than one prefix and one exponent. Double prefixes and other multiple prefixes (e.g. \milli\kilo), or double exponents and other multiple exponents (e.g. \tothe{2}\tothe{3}) are forbidden.

XML: The prefix and exponent strings used in XML shall not corrupt the requirements for a valid XML structure. The XML shall use encoding UTF-8. Requires external validation.

R010

It is not permitted to use any prefix in prior to one of the units \kilogram, \one, \decibel, \degreecelsius, \mmhg, \minute, \hour, \day. Prefixes are also not permitted for quantities of rotation with units \second\tothe{-1} and \minute\tothe{-1}.

XML: The prefix and unit used in XML shall not corrupt the requirements for a valid XML structure. The XML shall use encoding UTF-8. Requires external validation.

R011

It is not permitted to combine the unit \gram with prefix \kilo. Use \kilogram instead.

XML: The prefix and unit used in XML shall not corrupt the requirements for a valid XML structure. The XML shall use encoding UTF-8. Requires external validation.

R012

It is not permitted to combine the unit \bel with prefix \deci. Use \decibel instead.

XML: The prefix and unit used in XML shall not corrupt the requirements for a valid XML structure. The XML shall use encoding UTF-8. Requires external validation.

R013

It is not permitted to use units with exponents other than integer values and specific values for building roots of units that are '0.5', '+0.5' and '-0.5'.

XML: The exponent used in XML shall not corrupt the requirements for a valid XML structure. The XML shall use encoding UTF-8. Requires external validation.

R014

It is forbidden to use an exponent with unit \one.

XML: The exponent used in XML shall not corrupt the requirements for a valid XML structure. The XML shall use encoding UTF-8. Requires external validation.

R015

Components of units with a positive (or zero) exponent can be interpreted as the nominator of a fraction of units, whereby all units with negative exponent belong to the denominator. In such cases it is only permitted to have not more than one prefix in the nominator and not more than one prefix in the denominator.

XML: The prefix and unit used in XML shall not corrupt the requirements for a valid XML structure. The XML shall use encoding UTF-8. Requires external validation.

R016

The components ‘unitPhase’ and ‘listUnitPhase’ shall only be used with SI units for angles. These are: `\metre\tothe{0}`, `\metre\metre\tothe{-1}`, `\metre\tothe{-1}\metre`, `\radian`, `\radian` with a SI prefix, `\degree`, `\arcminute` and `\arcsecond`.

XML: The unit used in XML shall not corrupt the requirements for a valid XML structure. The XML shall use encoding UTF-8. Requires external validation.

R017

BIPM SI units in the quality class PLATINUM are `\kilogram`, `\metre`, `\second`, `\ampere`, `\kelvin`, `\mole`, `\candela`, `\one`, `\degree`, `\arcminute`, `\arcsecond`, `\day`, `\hour`, `\minute` (no use of prefixes).

XML: The unit used in XML shall not corrupt the requirements for a valid XML structure. The XML shall use encoding UTF-8. Requires external validation.

R018

BIPM SI units in the quality class GOLD are `\gram`, `\radian`, `\steradian`, `\hertz`, `\newton`, `\pascal`, `\joule`, `\watt`, `\coulomb`, `\volt`, `\farad`, `\ohm`, `\siemens`, `\weber`, `\tesla`, `\henry`, `\degreecelsius`, `\lumen`, `\lux`, `\becquerel`, `\sievert`, `\gray` and `\katal`. Platinum units (rule R017) will also be of quality class GOLD

if they are used with SI prefixes `\deca`, `\hecto`, `\kilo`, `\mega`, `\giga`, `\tera`, `\peta`, `\exa`, `\zetta`, `\yotta`, `\deci`, `\centi`, `\milli`, `\micro`, `\nano`, `\pico`, `\femto`, `\atto`, `\zepto` and `\yocto`.

XML: The unit used in XML shall not corrupt the requirements for a valid XML structure. The XML shall use encoding UTF-8. Requires external validation.

R019

BIPM SI units (non-SI units allowed with the SI) in the quality class SILVER are `\hectare`, `\litre`, `\tonne`, `\electronvolt`, `\dalton`, `\astronomicalunit`, `\neper`, `\bel` and `\decibel`.

XML: The unit used in XML shall not corrupt the requirements for a valid XML structure. The XML shall use encoding UTF-8. Requires external validation.

R020

BIPM SI units (non-SI units allowed with the 8th edition of the SI) in the quality class BRONZE are `\angstrom`, `\atomicunittime`, `\atomicmassunit`, `\bar`, `\barn`, `\clight`, `\electronmass`, `\elementarycharge`, `\knot`, `\mmhg`, `\naturalunittime`, `\nauticalmile`, `\hartree`, `\bohr` and `\planckbar`.

XML: The unit used in XML shall not corrupt the requirements for a valid XML structure. The XML shall use encoding UTF-8. Requires external validation.

R021

The format for time stamps must be conform to the time format for legal local time with UTC offset from ISO 8601. Time stamps are provided as 'YYYY-MM-DDThh:mm:ss.k...kOhh:mm' (Y-year, M-month, D-day, h-hour, m-minute, s-second, k - decimal places of second, ' ' and k are optional, O – sign '+' or '-'). This rule is applied to all 'dateTime' components.

XML: Implementation by dateTime type from XML specification. XML type allows required format and other formats not compatible to the D-SI requirement. The XML shall use encoding UTF-8. Requires external validation.

R022

The content of 'label' string is not regulated by the D-SI. Its length is arbitrary.

XML: The label string shall not corrupt the requirements for a valid XML structure. The XML shall use encoding UTF-8.

R023

The content of component 'distribution' shall be a non-empty UTF-8 formatted string. The length is arbitrary.

XML: The content of the distribution component shall not corrupt the requirements for a valid XML structure. The XML shall use encoding UTF-8. Requires external validation.

R024

All data for 'complex' elements shall either be provided in the Cartesian coordinate form (atomic components 'valueReal', 'valueImag' and 'unit') or in the polar coordinate form (atomic components 'valueMagnitude', 'valuePhase', 'unit' and 'unitPhase'). A mixture of the components from both forms inside one 'complex' element is not permitted.

XML: The rule is implemented in the XML scheme.

R025

If the component 'distribution' is used in elements of type constant, then the component 'uncertainty' must be provided as well.

XML: No additional constrain in the XML scheme. Requires external validation.

Specific rules for univariate uncertainty

R026

When using a statement of univariate uncertainty then it shall either be the sub type 'expandedUnc' or the sub type 'coverageInterval' but not both types at the same time. This

applies to the use of the univariate uncertainty in elements 'real' and 'listUnivariateUnc' (in list).

XML: The requirement is implemented in the XML reference scheme.

R027

When using the sub type 'coverageInterval' the value of component 'intervalMin' must be less than or equal to 'intervalMax'.

XML: No additional constrain in the XML scheme. Requires external validation.

R028

In a list of real elements, it is not permitted to use the component 'listUnivariateUnc' when at the same time the 'ellipsoidalRegion' or the 'rectangularRegion' element is used.

XML: No additional constrain in the XML scheme. Requires external validation.

R029

In a list of real elements, it is not permitted to use the component 'listUnivariateUnc' when less than two elements of type 'real' are defined.

XML: No additional constrain in the XML scheme. Requires external validation.

R030

In a list it is not permitted to use the component 'listUnivariateUnc' when the list contains 'complex' or 'list' elements.

XML: This rule is implemented by the XML scheme.

R031

The component 'listUnivariateUnc' must always be used together with the 'listUnit' component.

XML: No additional constrain in the XML scheme. Requires external validation.

Specific rules for multivariate uncertainty

R032

When using a statement of multivariate uncertainty, then it shall either be the sub type 'ellipsoidalRegion' or the sub type 'rectangularRegion' but not both types at the same time. This applies to the use of the multivariate uncertainty in elements 'complex', 'listBivariateUnc' (in list) and 'list' (multivariate uncertainty of all components in the list).

XML: The requirement is implemented in the XML reference scheme.

R033

The covariance matrix for a multivariate uncertainty must always be of dimension $n \times n$, where n is the dimension of the underlying elements. In case of a single complex element it must be $n=2$. For a list of m real elements, there must be $n=m$ and for a list of m complex elements there must be $n=2m$. In addition, the values should represent a symmetric matrix.

XML: No additional constrain in the XML scheme. Requires external validation. Thereby, the limited arithmetical precision of numerical values should be considered when checking the symmetry.

R034

The absolute correlation value for all covariance values (not on the main diagonal) of the covariance matrix should be less or equal to one.

XML: No additional constrain in the XML scheme. Requires external validation. Thereby, the limited arithmetical precision of numerical values should be considered.

R035

The units for variance values and covariance values in the covariance matrix should be products of the units from the underlying vector quantity. I.e., let $[A,B,C,D]$ be a vector of units for a vector quantity with four components (list of four real or list of two complex). Thereby, the order of the units refers to the

order of the components in list of real, list of complex and respectively in complex elements. The units in the covariance matrix should then be the products

$$\begin{bmatrix} A^*A & A^*B & A^*C & A^*D \\ B^*A & B^*B & B^*C & B^*D \\ C^*A & C^*B & C^*C & C^*D \\ D^*A & D^*B & D^*C & D^*D \end{bmatrix}.$$

For complex elements in Cartesian coordinate form the 'unit' component is used twice ([unit,unit]). For complex elements in polar coordinate form the order is [unit,unitPhase].

XML: The order of units refers to the top-to-bottom sequence of real elements and respectively complex elements in a list. Else there are no additional constrain in the XML scheme. Requires external validation.

R036

In a list of complex elements, it is not permitted to use the component 'listBivariateUnc' when at a different place in the list components 'ellipsoidalRegion' or 'rectangularRegion' are used.

XML: No additional constrain in the XML scheme. Requires external validation.

R037

In a list of complex elements, it is not permitted to use the component 'listBivariateUnc' when less than two elements of type 'complex' are defined.

XML: No additional constrain in the XML scheme. Requires external validation.

R038

In a list it is not permitted to use the component 'listBivariateUnc' when the list contains 'real' or 'list' elements.

XML: This rule is implemented by the XML scheme.

R039

The component 'listBivariateUnc' must always be used together with a) the 'listUnit' component if it refers to complex elements in Cartesian coordinate form and b) the 'listUnit' and 'listUnitPhase'

components if it refers to complex elements in polar coordinate form.

XML: No additional constrain in the XML scheme. Requires external validation.

R040

It is not permitted to use the sub types ‘ellipsoidalRegion’ and ‘rectangularRegion’ for a statement of multivariate uncertainty in lists with less than two real elements, lists with less than two complex elements and lists of lists.

XML: No additional constrain in the XML scheme. Requires external validation.

R041

All complex elements in a list must be of same kind of form (either only Cartesian or only polar coordinate form) if the component ‘listBivariateUnc’ is used.

XML: No additional constrain in the XML scheme. Requires external validation.

Additional rules for lists

R042

A list must at least contain one of the elements ‘real’, ‘complex’ or ‘list’.

XML: Requirement implemented in the XML scheme.

R043

A list shall not mix the elements ‘real’, ‘complex’ or ‘list’.

XML: Requirement implemented in the XML scheme.

R044

It is only permitted to use the component ‘listUnit’ if the list contains two or more real elements (respectively two or more complex elements).

XML: No additional constrain in the XML scheme. Requires external validation.

R045

It is only permitted to use the component 'listUnitPhase' if the list contains two or more complex elements.

XML: No additional constrain in the XML scheme. Requires external validation.

R046

If the list component 'listUnitPhase' is used, then all complex elements in the list must be of polar coordinate form.

XML: No additional constrain in the XML scheme. Requires external validation.

R047

In a list of complex elements, the component 'listUnitPhase' is only permitted to be used together with component 'listUnit' but never on its own.

XML: No additional constrain in the XML scheme. Requires external validation.

R048

Lists of real elements allow to define a component 'listUnit'. If 'listUnit' is used, then all real elements in the list shall not provide the component 'unit'.

XML: Do not write element '<si:unit>' in real elements in list, if '<si:listUnit>' is specified. Requires external validation.

R049

Lists of complex elements allow to define a component 'listUnit' and respectively 'listUnitPhase'. If 'listUnit' and respectively 'listUnitPhase' are used, then all complex elements in the list shall neither provide the component 'unit' nor 'unitPhase'.

XML: Do not write element '<si:unit>' or '<si:unitPhase>' in complex elements in list, if '<si:listUnit>' or '<si:listUnitPhase>' are specified. Requires external validation.

R050

Lists of real elements allow to define a component 'listUnivariateUnc'. If 'listUnivariateUnc' is used, then all real elements in the list shall neither provide the sub types 'expandedUnc' nor 'coverageInterval'.

XML: Do not write element '<si:expandedUnc>' or '<si:coverageInterval>' in real elements in list, if '<si:listUnivariateUnc>' is specified. Requires external validation.

R051

Lists of complex elements allow to define a component 'listBivariateUnc'. If 'listBivariateUnc' is used, then all complex elements in the list shall neither provide the sub types 'ellipsoidalRegion' nor 'rectangularRegion'.

XML: Do not write element '<si:ellipsoidalRegion>' or '<si:rectangularRegion>' in complex elements in list, if '<si:listBivariateUnc>' is specified. Requires external validation.

Specific rules for hybrid

R052

Each hybrid element shall contain at least one element of type 'real', 'complex', 'constant' or 'list'.

XML: Requirement implemented in the XML scheme.

R053

The first element in a hybrid data model shall be conform to all rules R001 – R051.

XML: Requirement implemented in the XML scheme as described at rules R001-R051.

R054

The quality class for hybrid data is the one associated with the first element in hybrid but not better than GOLD. The quality class can be further reduced, if rule R055 is not satisfied.

XML: No additional constrain in the XML scheme. Requires external validation.

R055

All elements in hybrid shall be of the same element type, i.e. either all of type 'real', type 'complex', type 'constant' or type 'list'.

XML: Requirement implemented in the XML scheme.

Summary of D-SI data models

The following data models use a notation which indicates optional components by adding symbol '(o)' and mandatory elements by symbol '(m)'. The components of an element of a data model are written from left to right in the sequence as it is required by rule R002. For some of the elements a choice from alternative components is possible. Such alternative choices are separated by 'or' (i.e. 'A' or 'B'). If a component is repeated n times, then the symbol '[1..n]' is appended to the name of t component.

M01

The data model for the real element is

'label' (o), 'value' (m), 'unit' (m), 'dateTime' (o), 'expandedUnc' or 'coverageInterval' (o).

M02

The data model for the expandedUnc element is

'uncertainty' (m), 'coverageFactor' (m), 'coverageProbability' (m), 'distribution' (o).

M03

The data model for the coverageInterval element is

'standardUnc' (m), 'intervalMin' (m), 'intervalMax' (m), 'coverageProbability' (m), 'distribution' (o).

M04

The data model for constant element is

'label' (o), 'value' (m), 'unit' (m), 'dateTime' (o), 'uncertainty' (o), 'distribution' (o).

M05

The data model for the complex element in Cartesian coordinate form is

'label' (o), 'valueImag' (m), 'valueReal' (m), 'unit' (m), 'dateTime' (o), 'ellipsoidalRegion' or 'rectangularRegion' (o).

M06

The data model for the complex element in polar coordinate form is

'label' (o), 'valueMagnitude' (m), 'valuePhase' (m), 'unit' (m), 'unitPhase' (m), 'dateTime' (o), 'ellipsoidalRegion' or 'rectangularRegion' (o).

M07

The data model for both the ellipsoidalRegion element and the rectangularRegion element is

'covarianceMatrix' (m), 'coverageFactor' (m), 'coverageProbability' (m), 'distribution' (o).

M08

The data model for the covarianceMatrix element is

'column' [1..n] (m)

where the data model for the column element is

'covariance' [1..n] (m)

and the data model for the covariance element is

'value' (m), 'unit' (m).

M09

The data model for a list of real elements is

'label' (o), 'dateTime' (o), 'listUnit' (o), 'listUnivariateUnc' (o), 'real' [1..n] (m), 'ellipsoidalRegion' or 'rectangularRegion' (m).

M10

The data model for a list of complex elements in Cartesian coordinate form is

'label' (o), 'dateTime' (o), 'listUnit' (o), 'listBivariateUnc' (o), 'complex' [1..n] (m), 'ellipsoidalRegion' or 'rectangularRegion' (o).

M11

The data model for a list of complex elements in polar coordinate form is

'label' (o), 'dateTime' (o), 'listUnit' (o), 'listUnitPhase' (o), 'listBivariateUnc' (o), 'complex' [1..n] (m), 'ellipsoidalRegion' or 'rectangularRegion' (o).

M12

The data model for a list of list elements is

'label' (o), 'dateTime' (o), 'list' [1..n] (m).

M13

The data model for hybrid elements is

'real' [1..n] or 'complex' [1..n] or 'constant' [1..n] or 'list' [1..n] (m).

Data inside the D-SI in the responsibility of the user

The D-SI data model is only providing a data structure with minimum required information for a universal exchange of metrological data in digital formats. It helps the user to exchange complete metrological information. Still it is the responsibility of the user to fill in the correct data to the model. I. e. in case of a univariate uncertainty, the user has to make sure that the values provided for uncertainty, coverage factor, coverage probability

and statistical are representing correct information from a mathematical perspective.

The following list provides detailed information to facilitate the user's understanding of data in his responsibility.

D01

The user can utilize the label components in each D-SI data model element to identify the quantities underlying to the D-SI element according to his needs (i.e. by using own terminology or controlled vocabularies for quantities). Thereby, the user should ensure, that the units provided with the data elements are valid units in the scope of the underlying quantity.

D02

The component 'unit' is the reference unit for the numerical values provided by the components 'value', 'valueImag', 'valueReal', 'valueMagnitude', 'uncertainty', 'standardUnc', 'intervalMin' and 'intervalMax'. In the context of a list, 'unit' is replaced as reference by the component 'listUnit' if 'listUnit' is provided.

D03

The component 'unitPhase' is the reference unit for the numerical value provided by the component 'valuePhase'. In the context of a list, 'unitPhase' is replaced as reference by the component 'listUnitPhase' if 'listUnitPhase' is provided.

D04

If a unit is assigned with an exponent, then the exponent is applied to the unit and, if defined, a prefix in prior to the unit (i.e. \kilo\metre\tothe{3} is equivalent to 10^9 m^3).

D05

All numerical values are absolute values. Relative information like relative uncertainty shall not be provided.

D06

The user has to ensure, that the numerical data for a real quantity with an expanded uncertainty and respectively with a coverage interval is correct from a mathematical perspective.

D07

For multivariate quantities (complex, list of real and list of complex), the user has to make sure, that the numerical data for multivariate uncertainty (ellipsoidal region and rectangular region) is correct from a mathematical point of view.

D08

The components inside the covariance matrix have to be filled in in the right order according to the underlying quantity (complex, list of real and list of complex).

D09

The correct variance values and covariance values shall be filled into the covariance matrix and no standard uncertainties.

D10

If a unit in the covariance matrix (product of two units) is not conform to the rules for providing units of the BIPM SI brochure (i.e. R015 not holding), then the user is responsible to normalise the units inside the underlying quantities. This can comprise a normalisation inside the components 'unit' and 'unitphase' in a complex element, 'unit' in real elements in a list, 'unit' and 'unitPhase' in complex elements in a list and 'listUnit' as well as 'listUnitPhase' in a list. Thereby, normalisation of a unit means to remove SI prefixes from the unit expression by adjusting the exponent of all associated numerical values.

D11

The quantities inside hybrid elements should provide equivalent quantities. Thereby the user should ensure, that conversion between a numerical value referring to non-SI units a numerical value referring to SI units was made sufficiently accurate (correct).

This responsibility also includes, that the elements listed in hybrid should provide the same data structure as the first element in hybrid – the SI element. Therefore, a user should provide data with the same dimensions, uncertainty models and the coordinate form (in the complex case).

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